

Data Management Plan for the Project “Latvian Folklore Studies in Exile”

Version 1

Description

The project aims to create new knowledge about the disciplinary history of Latvian folkloristics in exile from 1944 to 1990. The research data acquisition will result in 3 public datasets: “Bibliographical data: books”, “Bibliographical data: publications in press and periodicals”, and “Archival data”. Additionally, a set of expert interviews and an online survey will be conducted, which will constitute restricted research data.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Latvian Folklore Studies in Exile
(Izp-2024/1-0522)

Researchers

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Organizations

Institute of Literature, Folklore and Art of the University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan for the Project “Latvian Folklore Studies in Exile”](#)

Description:

The project aims to create new knowledge about the disciplinary history of Latvian folkloristics in exile from 1944 to 1990. The research data acquisition will result in 3 public datasets: “Bibliographical data: books”, “Bibliographical data: publications in press and periodicals”, and “Archival data”. Additionally, a set of expert interviews and an online survey will be conducted, which will constitute restricted research data.

Researchers:

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [Latvian Folklore Studies in Exile \(lzp-2024/1-0522\)](#)

Project: [Cite Project](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-03-31](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Bibliographical data: publications in press and periodicals

The dataset offers structured bibliographic data: these are references to publications of the Latvian exile press and periodicals that deal with Latvian folklore issues. These Latvian newspapers and magazines published in Sweden, Germany, the US, Canada, Australia, and other countries cover the period from 1944 to 1990. By collecting, verifying, and organizing bibliographic data, we aim to create a fundamental research basis for the diverse investigations of Latvian folklore studies and Latvian culture in exile.

The bibliographic dataset includes a metadata table describing each publication in detail. The table contains the following sections: author's surname and first name, publication year, article title, press publication, issue number, publication date, pages, place of publication, publication type (scientific article, review, folklore, letters, programs, event overviews, biographical materials, interview, memoirs, etc.), notes, and an annotation about the specific press publication. This structure provides complete and consistent information about each source, facilitating data retrieval, analysis, and citation.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

By collecting, verifying, and organizing bibliographic data, we aim to create a fundamental research basis for the diverse investigations of Latvian folklore studies and Latvian culture in exile.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Bibliographic data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There are no similar data available in an equally systematized way.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers and students in various humanities and social sciences fields: history, folklore studies, etc.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Excel, Notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Rita Grīnvalde (0000-0002-2998-3579)
- Elīna Gailīte (orcid: [0000-0002-3448-992X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3448-992X))

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Institutional PC and server (also: Google Drive, project's folder)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Bibliographical data: books

The dataset offers structured bibliographic data: these are references to Latvian exile books that deal with Latvian folklore issues.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

By collecting, verifying, and organizing bibliographic data, we aim to create a fundamental research basis for the diverse investigations of Latvian folklore studies and Latvian culture in exile.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Bibliographic data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There are no similar data available in an equally systematized way.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers and students in various humanities and social sciences fields: history, folklore studies, etc.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

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Yes

DOI

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Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Word, Adobe Acrobat Reader, Notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

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3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Institutional PC and server (also: Google Drive, project's folder)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Archival data

The dataset presents overview of collections in various memory institutions in Latvia and abroad containing documents on Latvian folklore studies in exile.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

By detecting archival data, we aim to create a fundamental research basis for the diverse investigations of Latvian folklore studies and Latvian culture in exile.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Archival collection descriptions

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There are no similar data available in an equally systematized way.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers and students in various humanities and social sciences fields: history, folklore studies, etc.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Word, Adobe Acrobat Reader, Notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

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3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Institutional PC and server (also: Google Drive, project's folder)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Interviews

A set of at least 6 quality interviews with the experts, folklore researchers and personalities who were active in the exile Academia. The interview recordings and transcripts will be included in the Digital Archives of Latvian Folklore, garamantas.lv, collection LFK [2250].

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The interviews contribute to historiographical knowledge for further investigations of Latvian folklore studies and Latvian culture in exile.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Interviews (life stories)

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- MP3

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

These experts will be interviewed for the first time for particular research purpose.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers in humanities and social sciences.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

Other

In accordance with the principles of the Digital Archives of Latvian Folklore, garamantas.lv.

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Public accessibility of the interviews will be determined in accordance with consent of each informant. The survey responses are expected to serve as a complementary source to be incorporated into scholarly articles. Ethical principles will be ensured according to ILFA's Privacy Policy and EU Regulation 2016/679. To establish high standards of conduct for the archival materials gathered during the implementation of the project, the Code of Ethics of the International Councils of Archives will be taken into consideration and the following points will be abided: the integrity of archival material will be protected, thus guaranteeing that it continues to be reliable evidence of the past in the future; the authenticity of materials gathered will be protected during archival processing, preservation, and use; the continuing accessibility and intelligibility of archival materials will be ensured; respect for both access and privacy and act within the boundaries of relevant the legislation will be ensured.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

<https://garamantas.lv/>

<https://garamantas.lv/>

The organisation's own repository with content at a level that is recognisable and relevant to the sector.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Word, Adobe Acrobat Reader, Notepad, MP3 player

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Institutional server and cloud

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Possibly contains sensitive personal information (therefore, the data won't be made public). Accessibility of the interviews will be determined in accordance with consent of each informant.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Ethical principles will be ensured according to ILFA's Privacy Policy and EU Regulation 2016/679. To establish high standards of conduct for the archival materials gathered during the implementation of the project, the Code of Ethics of the International Councils of Archives will be taken into consideration and the following points will be abided: the integrity of archival material will be protected, thus guaranteeing that it continues to be reliable evidence of the past in the

future; the authenticity of materials gathered will be protected during archival processing, preservation, and use; the continuing accessibility and intelligibility of archival materials will be ensured; respect for both access and privacy and act within the boundaries of relevant the legislation will be ensured.

Online survey data

The data collected via the online survey “Latvian folklore in exile”. Respondents will be asked about various traditional cultural practices in exile, with the option to answer anonymously. The Digital Archives of Latvian Folklore and, garamantas.lv, in particular, its online survey tool, “ALF Asks” (“LFK jautā”), will serve for creation of the online survey.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The survey responses will contribute to historiographical knowledge on Latvian folklore studies and Latvian culture in exile. The obtained data are expected to serve as a complementary source to be incorporated into project team’s scholarly articles.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- HTML
- PDF
- CSV
- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No such survey has been implemented before this project.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers in humanities and social sciences.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Possibly contains sensitive personal information (therefore, the data won't be made public).

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

garamantas.lv

<https://garamantas.lv/>

The organisation's own repository with content at a level that is recognisable and relevant to the sector. The online survey tool embedded in the platform is important for the implementation of the project activities.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

MS Word, Adobe Acrobat Reader, Notepad

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Rita Grīnvalde (0000-0002-2998-3579)
- Digne Ūdre (0000-0003-2424-2517)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Institutional server and cloud

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

Possibly contains sensitive personal information (therefore, the data won't be made public). Accessibility of the interviews will be determined in accordance with consent of each informant.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Privacy constraints
- Privacy policies

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